

RESISTANT HYPERTENSION: PATHOGENESIS AND RISK FACTORS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *In clinical practice, the concept of resistant arterial hypertension has become increasingly relevant in recent years. Clinical inertia, defined as the failure of the clinician to increase therapy when the treatment goal is not achieved, is a major factor in suboptimal medical treatment leading to uncontrolled hypertension. Lack of knowledge of treatment guidelines, underestimation of cardiovascular risk, and use of false reasons for avoiding intensification of therapy (e.g., physician perception [without patient input] that the patient will not take more medications) are common causes of clinical inertia.*

Keywords: *resistant arterial hypertension, CKD, hyperaldosteronism.*

The International Society of Hypertension's 2020 Global Hypertension Practice Guidelines define persistent or resistant hypertension (RAH) as blood pressure (BP) measured greater than 140/90 mmHg Art. in the physician's office in patients taking ≥ 3 antihypertensive medications (including diuretics) at doses that are either optimal or maximally tolerated after ruling out pseudoresistance [1]. Resistant arterial hypertension (RAH) is important both because of its high prevalence and its associated risks. Regarding the prevalence of true resistant hypertension, the Global Hypertension Practice Guidelines estimate that approximately 10% of the hypertensive population is present [2]. Many authors indicate figures from 10 to 20% without distinguishing between true or apparent resistant hypertension [2]. Indeed, at the lower threshold (130/80 mmHg) recommended by the 2018 American Heart Association (AHA) Guidelines, the prevalence of resistant hypertension is higher (20%). Another source, Hypertension Canada's 2020 Review of Evidence and Recommendations, lists the prevalence of resistant hypertension as 10–30% [3]. On the other hand, the expected prevalence of true resistant hypertension in another study was 2%. A meta-analysis including 91 epidemiological studies and 3,207,911 patients with hypertension showed that the prevalence of true resistant hypertension and pseudo-resistant hypertension was approximately 10% each. Moreover, an earlier meta-analysis, including more than 1,000,000 patients and more than 12,700,000 person-years, showed at least a two-fold difference in mortality rates from coronary heart disease, stroke, and other vascular diseases for every 20 increase in usual SBP mmHg Art. [1,4]. Assuming that the prevalence of hypertension exceeds 1 billion patients and the prevalence of resistant hypertension is at least 10%, then these different thresholds for resistant hypertension affect more than 100 million patients worldwide [5]. Poor adherence to prescribed medication regimens is a common problem in patients with high blood pressure and a common cause of uncontrolled hypertension. There is evidence that poor adherence is less common in patients managed by hypertension specialists [6].

Factors contributing to the development of resistant arterial hypertension are an increase in total fluid volume. Volume expansion associated with excess dietary sodium intake, sodium retention due to chronic kidney disease (CKD), and/or inappropriate use of diuretics can cause persistent hypertension. Diuretics are the mainstay of treatment in patients whose blood pressure cannot be controlled with multiple drugs from other classes, and reducing dietary salt intake is a

useful adjunctive treatment in patients with resistant hypertension [6]. Obesity is common in patients with resistant arterial hypertension. Data from the Hypertension and Diabetes Risk Screening and Awareness (HYDRA) study, a cross-sectional study of 45,125 primary care patients, showed that those with a body mass index greater than 40 kg/m² had a higher prevalence of hypertension, as well as the likelihood of needing 4 or 3 antihypertensive drugs to achieve blood pressure control. It was 5.3 and 3.2 times higher, respectively, compared with patients with normal weight (body mass index < 25 kg/m²). Increased sodium and fluid retention, activation of the sympathetic nervous system, and stimulation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) appear to contribute to high blood pressure levels in obese individuals [7,8]. Hyperaldosteronism is the most common cause of secondary hypertension and often contributes to treatment resistance. Hypokalemia and adrenal tumors are no longer necessary for the diagnosis of hyperaldosteronism. In fact, a significant proportion of patients with hyperaldosteronism have normal potassium levels. Experimental and clinical evidence suggests that the cardiorenal effects of excess aldosterone are dependent on concomitant high salt intake in the diet [9]. Due to the high prevalence of hyperaldosteronism in this patient group, all patients with resistant hypertension, even those with normokalemia, should be screened for hyperaldosteronism. The measurement of the ratio of plasma aldosterone concentration (PAC) to plasma renin activity (PRA) (≥ 20) has sufficient sensitivity and specificity to be used as an effective screening test for hyperaldosteronism. Confirmation of increased 24-hour urinary excretion of aldosterone confirms the diagnosis of hyperaldosteronism. After confirmation of biochemical hyperaldosteronism, abdominal computed tomography is recommended to detect adrenal tumors. Even with confirmed biochemical hyperaldosteronism, the CT image has low specificity for detecting functional adenomas producing aldosterone. Blood sampling from the adrenal veins can confirm or exclude aldosterone excretion, which corresponds to unilateral adenoma [9,10].

Obstructive sleep apnea. Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), characterized by sustained and increased respiratory efforts despite partial or complete occlusion of the upper respiratory tract, is a common observation in patients with resistant hypertension. In our clinic, it was noted that 85% of patients with resistant hypertension have OSA, defined as the apnea-hypopnea index ≥ 5 events per hour. OSA should be assessed by nocturnal polysomnography in patients with symptoms of OSA, such as daytime drowsiness and restless sleep. There is a link between excess aldosterone, obesity and sleep apnea. Stimulation of aldosterone release by visceral fat, excessive sodium retention stimulated by sympathetic activation, and hypoxemia are possible underlying mechanisms. Treatment using continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) is the gold standard for the management of OSA; however, the role of CPAP in the treatment of hypertension is not fully established. Although the causal relationship between CCA and resistant hypertension cannot be unambiguously established, patients with resistant hypertension and OSA should receive CPAP treatment and weight loss should be recommended [8,11].

Chronic kidney disease. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a common cause of resistant arterial hypertension and a consequence of prolonged uncontrolled blood pressure. Fluid retention, excessive activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) and the use of concomitant medications such as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are associated with resistance to treatment in patients with impaired renal function. All patients with resistant arterial hypertension should have an assessment of glomerular filtration rate using the Modification of Diet in Renal Disease formula or the Cockcroft-Gault equation, since serum

creatinine levels are an unreliable marker of CKD, especially in elderly patients. The value of albuminuria should also be assessed [4,12]. RAAS blockade in patients with CKD reduces cardiovascular risk, improves blood pressure control and reduces proteinuria, as well as slows down the progression to end-stage renal failure.

Renal artery stenosis. Renovascular diseases are a common observation in patients with hypertension who have multiple risk factors and extrarenal atherosclerotic diseases, especially among patients with resistant arterial hypertension. The vast majority (90%) of renal artery lesions have an atherosclerotic etiology, and the prevalence of these diseases increases with age [13]. Patients with resistant arterial hypertension and known atherosclerotic diseases, declining kidney function or a history of sudden pulmonary edema have an increased likelihood of atherosclerotic damage to the renal arteries and should be examined for renal artery stenosis. The choice of treatment for atherosclerotic lesions of the renal arteries is controversial due to the lack of convincing evidence in favor of both drug treatment and revascularization [14].

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